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**SYSTEM OF VALUES IN AN IMPERFECT FAMILY WITHIN THE
FRAMEWORK OF SCIENTIST THEORY**

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Abstract This article analyzes concepts such as "values" and "value orientations". Different approaches to the study of values are considered in psychology, philosophy, and sociology.

Key words: value, incomplete family, scientific theory.

The main part Value directions are one of the main structural forms of a mature person. In fact, this is the problem of the meaning of human existence developed by representatives of various scientific schools: philosophy, sociology, psychology. It is believed that the concept of value was first introduced by Immanuel Kant in his Critique of Pure Reason. The philosopher contrasted the realm of morality (freedom) with the realm of nature (necessity) and developed the idea of the "right world" (the world of values and norms) as opposed to the "world of being." At the beginning of the 20th century. German philosopher and psychologist G. Münsterberg gave an analysis of the world of values. Believing that nature is generally devoid of values and that individuals know only conditional values in their interactions, he for the first time in the history of axiological thought presented a system of values schematically in the form of a table. the legality of the structure of the person's all-encompassing worldview, his appreciation of the world is reflected. After I. Kant and R. Münsterberg, representatives of neo-Kantianism turned to the problem of values. W. Windelband, G. Rickert. Thus, G. Rickert developed the doctrine of values as the basis of the theory of true knowledge and moral action. Knowing, according to G. Rickert, means taking a certain position in relation to values³. The German philosopher W. Windelband created the subject of knowledge, which he believed to be certain rules of connecting ideas of people and for correct thinking, and recognized the truth as the highest value as the highest criterion.

According to the modern researcher P.E. Matveev, Windelband and Rickert were largely engaged in the philosophical justification of the existence of values, and justified the existence of a special aspect of individual phenomena that are values. It is of great interest for a deeper study of the problem of trends. Sociologists M. Weber and E. Durkheim were the first to touch on the issue of values, and they justified the need to study values in the science of sociology and defined society as a normative-value system. who have made important contributions to understanding as T. Parsons considered the problem of values within the framework of his theory of social systems. According to the sociologist, values are the basis for the integration of subjects into society through the interdependence between social and personal systems.

In the science of psychology, great attention is also paid to the problem of value orientations. In 1968, the famous American psychologist A. Maslow devoted a separate chapter to the problem of values in his book "Toward the Psychology of Being". He interpreted value as a selective attitude arising from needs, and sometimes identified needs and values as "hierarchically and evolutionarily linked." Unlike Maslow, W. Frankl introduced the idea of \u200b\u200bvalues as semantic universals - what is crystallized as a result of the generalization of the usual situations of society or people, and what has social value as a result of social life, upbringing, etc., has personal value at the same time. 'ladi, these goods and values, which are objective in the process of social life, should be engaged with the goals of individual activity.

In the mid-60s. 20th century The concept of "value orientations" began to be widely used in local scientific literature. V. B. Olshansky, A. G. Zdravomyslov and V. A. Yadov are the first scientists to study the problem of the direction of value. In their works, value orientations are first of all related to the concepts of attitude and orientation of the individual. In turn, the beginning of the widespread use of the "value" category in psychology was laid by V. P. Tugarinov. According to him, value is "objects, events and their characteristics, as well as ideas and motivations as a norm, goal or ideal, which are necessary as a means of satisfying the needs and interests of a certain society or class and individual". Psychological category as value is considered in the works of S. L. Rubinshtein, D. A. Leontyev, L. I. Bojovich, V. N. Myasishchev. "In the process of social life," he wrote. S. L. Rubinstein, - public goods and values are emphasized, which act as objective values independently of drivers for the individual.

D.A. Leontiev also connects the process of socialization with the individual's value orientation: "...value orientations are technical and refer to the study of individual or group ideas about the important value system that determines the general directions for their life activities directed. These ideas are formed in the process of socialization, through the "internalization" of group and general structural values. L. I. Bojovich recognizes the development of a person's motivational sphere, his needs, desires, aspirations and intentions as the central link of personality formation. According to the psychologist, the acquisition of certain moral values as the dominant motives of behavior occurs with the most perfect hierarchically developed structure of the motivational sphere. The approach to personal values from the point of view of the analysis of mutual relations was developed by V. N. Myasishchev. In his opinion, the objects and events of reality connected with a person through social relations act as if they are objectively included in his life world and activity, they acquire personal significance and value.

Summary

Family relations are a separate world with its own value system, a world where individual and collective principles are combined. Traditionally, the family was considered the guardian of values and traditions. Through the family, many spiritual values, moral standards and everyday experiences are passed on to new generations. Therefore, it is very important to note that family values begin to form between spouses in the first years of marriage. The first years of life together are the first stage of the family life cycle, the formation of individual communication stereotypes, the coordination of the value system and the development of a common ideological position. In fact, at this stage, there is a mutual adaptation of the couple, a search for the type of relationship that will satisfy both of them. Spouses face the task of forming a family structure, dividing functions between husband and wife, and developing common family values. Family values express the attitude of the couple about why the family exists and what it should bring to them¹⁷. These values form a hierarchical scale: most importantly, without them, a person considers the family incomplete, insignificant. According to the scale of family values, a person manifests himself in a number of family activities.

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